

State Estimation for Agile Quadrotors in the Wild

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Abstract—In this extended abstract, we present our latest research in robust state estimation for agile quadrotor flight. We discuss the differences between discrete- and continuous-time trajectory representations in visual-inertial odometry (VIO). Then, we present a novel VIO algorithm that combines events and standard frames to estimate the pose of a quadrotor subject to a rotor failure. Finally, we discuss our recent progress in learned inertial odometry for quadrotor flight. We conclude with the next research directions that have the potential to improve the robustness of onboard state estimation systems for autonomous drones.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quadrotors are among the most used mobile robotic platforms. Making them autonomous is crucial for time-critical missions, such as search and rescue, aerial delivery, reconnaissance, and even flying cars [1]. Robust state estimation using onboard sensing and computation is essential to achieve autonomous quadrotor flight in the wild. However, developing state estimators that are robust to the conditions encountered in time-critical missions is challenging and still unsolved.

The best viable solution for state estimation of flying vehicles with onboard sensing and computation is VIO. VIO fuses camera and IMU measurements and provides accurate and robust state estimation for many robotic applications [2]. However, it fails in scenarios characterized by low light, low texture, high dynamic range, and motion blur due to unreliable camera measurements and the drift that quickly accumulates when relying on IMU integration alone. These failure cases are often present in quadrotor flights during time-critical missions.

In this extended abstract, we summarize our latest research in state estimation for quadrotor flight in challenging environments. In Section II, we discuss the differences between discrete- and continuous-time trajectory representations in VIO and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM). In Section III, we present a novel VIO algorithm that combines events and standard frames to estimate the pose of a quadrotor subject to a rotor failure. In Section IV, we discuss the recent progresses in inertial odometry for pedestrian motion and its potential application for agile quadrotor flights.

II. TRAJECTORY REPRESENTATION IN SLAM

The vision-based SLAM discrete-time formulations has the advantage of a consolidated theory and very good understanding of success and failure cases. However, discrete-time SLAM needs customized algorithms to include asynchronous measurements coming from different sources in the estimation process. Similarly, ad-hoc solutions are needed to avoid adding a new state to the estimation problem every time a new measurement is available. Conversely, continuous-time SLAM

Fig. 1. Estimating the state of a quadrotor with complete failure of a rotor using only onboard sensing and computation is challenging due to the fast yaw rotation, over 20 rad/s (top figure), that causes motion blur. **Bottom Left:** standard frame with motion blur. **Bottom Center:** Events only (blue: positive events, red: negative events). **Bottom Right:** Event frame generated from events. Blue circles are detected and green dots are tracked features.

does not suffer from these limitations. It does not require tailored algorithms to integrate asynchronous or continuous high-rate sensor data, enabling the fusion of multiple sensor modalities in an intuitive fashion. On the down side, continuous time introduces a prior that could worsen the trajectory estimates in some unfavorable situations. In our work [3], we systematically compare the advantages and limitations of the two formulations in vision-based SLAM. To do so, we perform an extensive experimental analysis varying the quadrotor speed of motion and sensor modalities. Our experimental analysis suggests that, independently of the trajectory type, continuous-time SLAM is superior to its discrete counterpart whenever the sensors are not time-synchronized.

III. ONBOARD STATE ESTIMATION FOR AUTONOMOUS QUADROTOR FLIGHT DESPITE ROTOR FAILURE

Safety is a major concern that hinders the expansion of the drone industry. For this reason, it is crucial to develop methods to prevent quadrotors from crashing after motor failures. Reliable state estimation using only onboard sensing and computation is required to guarantee safety of quadrotors subject to a rotor failure during autonomous flights. Complete failure of a rotor results in a fast spinning motion (> 20

Fig. 2. **Left:** Perceptual challenges in drone racing: low light, motion blur, high dynamic range, and low texture. **Right:** Comparison of our inertial odometry, IO (ours), against a classical visual-inertial odometry, VIO, and a visual-inertial odometry using gate detection, Gate-IO.

rad/s) of the quadrotor. This high-speed motion brings a significant challenge to onboard state-estimation methods. In vision-based estimators, it causes motion blur (bottom left plot in Fig. 1). Such motion blur deteriorates feature detection and tracking and subsequently degrades visual-inertial odometry (VIO) performance, especially in low-light environments.

In our work [4], we propose a novel state-estimation algorithm combining measurements from an IMU, a range sensor, and a vision sensor that can be either a standard camera or an event camera. We show that an event camera becomes advantageous in low-light environments because the sensor does not suffer from motion blur and has a very high dynamic range. We achieve and demonstrate the first closed-loop flight of a quadrotor subjected to complete failure of a rotor, using only onboard sensors and computation. This work won the Robotics and Automation Letters (RA-L) best paper award in 2021 and the NASA Tech Briefs "Create the Future" award in Aerospace and Defense category in 2021.

IV. INERTIAL ODOMETRY FOR AGILE QUADROTORS

Inertial odometry is a very promising solution for 6-DoF pose estimation of pedestrian motion. Recent research [5] has shown that relatively shallow neural networks can learn motion priors for pedestrians from the repetitive pattern of the human gait. However, these methods fail when the IMU follows arbitrary motions, such as the ones of drones.

Our current research tackles the problem of using inertial odometry for autonomous drone racing. Drone racing requires flying a drone through a sequence of gates in minimum time and has now become a benchmark for the development of new drone technologies that can be turned into real-world products. What makes drone racing challenging is that the platform is flown at incredible speeds, over a hundred kilometers per hour, pushing the boundaries of the physics of the vehicle. Classical VIO systems fail in this scenario due to low light, low texture, high dynamic range, and motion blur (cf. Fig. 2).

We propose a learning-based odometry algorithm that uses an off-the-shelf IMU as the only sensor modality. Our algorithm combines a kinematic motion model—driven by the

IMU measurements—with a learned motion prior—driven by the commanded collective thrust. Our neural network architecture takes as input a time window of commanded thrust and gyroscope measurements and outputs an estimate of the distance travelled by the quadrotor in this time window. These relative displacements are then used to update an Extended Kalman filter (EKF), which is propagated using a kinematic motion model based on the IMU. We show that our approach is by far superior to the state-of-the-art commercial VIO system¹ and achieves comparable performance to the ad-hoc VIO which relies on a camera to perform gate detection (cf. Fig. 2). The ad-hoc VIO, named Gate-IO in Fig. 2, has access to the position of the gates in the track.

V. THE WAY FORWARD

We have shown how to improve classical VIO algorithms in the situations where standard camera measurements are not reliable.

We used an event camera to make VIO more robust against the large motion blur that is seen onboard a quadrotor subject to a rotor failure. Event cameras are a great complementary sensor to standard cameras thanks to their low latency and high dynamic range. Combining events and standard frames can make robotic perception more robust against motion blur and low light conditions. However, how to fully exploit the low latency and high dynamic range of the events is still an open question. In our work, we collected events in a small period of time to make what we called event frame. This representation of the events does not fully leverage their low latency. A promising direction in event-aided VIO is to use direct methods [6] to estimate the motion in the blind time of the standard camera.

Inertial odometry has the great potential to remove many of the failure cases of VIO related to challenging perceptual conditions. Our work on drone racing shows that inertial odometry can be used to estimate the state of the quadrotor in agile flights. However, its generalization capabilities are still a

¹<https://www.intelrealsense.com/tracking-camera-t265/>

weakness. Improving generalization of inertial odometry is an interesting venue for future work. Possible approaches could use additional proprioceptive sensors [7], e.g. rotor speeds, and learned-aided models of the drone dynamics [8], to limit the drift that accumulates in inertial odometry.

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